

ISSN (o): 3030-3362

N^o 4(13)

IV. 2024

RESEARCH AND IMPLEMENTATION
TADQIQ VA TATBIQ
ILMIY-USLUBIY JURNALI

CERTIFICATE
N^o 078777

INDEX COPERNICUS
INTERNATIONAL

- ✓ ANIQ FANLAR
- ✓ TABIIY FANLAR
- ✓ SIYOSIY FANLAR
- ✓ IJTIMOY FANLAR

- ✓ IQTISOD FANLARI
- ✓ TEXNIKA FANLARI
- ✓ TIBBIYOT FANLARI
- ✓ PEDAGOGIKA FANLARI

Bosh muharrir:

F.M.Muxtarov
t.f.b. PhD, dotsent

Jurnal oyda bir
marta nashr etiladi.

Nashr tillari:

O'zbek, rus, ingliz va
qoraqalpoq

O'zbekiston Respublikasi
Prezidenti Administratsiyasi
huzuridagi
Axborot va ommaviy
kommunikatsiya agentligida
2023-yil 3-mayda
№078777
raqam bilan ro'yxatga
olingan

Murojaat uchun

 [@fer_teach_uz](https://t.me/fer_teach_uz)
 +99893-343-13-14
 <https://fer-teach.uz/rai>

Mas'ul muharrir

S.I.Zokirov - f.-m.f.b. PhD., TATU Farg'ona filiali, Farg'ona, O'zbekiston.

Taxrir hay'ati:

B.R.Ismailov – t.f.d., prof. MAvezov Jan. Qoz. Univ-ti., Chimkent, Qozog'iston

I.Byorno - Ph.D., Imeritus, Daniya Texnika Universiteti, Kopengagen, Daniya

L.K.Mamadaliyeva – t.f.d. (DSc), prof. FarPI, Farg'ona, O'zbekiston

M.E.Yunusaliyev – t.f.d. (DSc), prof. FarPI, Farg'ona, O'zbekiston

X.B.Ismailov- t.f.n., dot., MAvezov Jan. Qoz. Univ-ti., Chimkent, Qozog'iston

J.T.Moldaliyev - bio. f. n., dotsent. OshDU, Osh, Qirg'iziston

T.M.Abdullayev – t.f.b. Ph.D., TATU Farg'ona filiali, Farg'ona, O'zbekiston.

N.I.Ibrokhimov – f.-m.f.b. Ph.D., TATU Farg'ona filiali, Farg'ona, O'zbekiston.

A.R.Nurmatov – tarix f.b. Ph.D., NamDU, Farg'ona, O'zbekiston.

D.F.To'xtasinov - ped.f.b. Ph.D., TATU Farg'ona filiali, Farg'ona, O'zbekiston.

S.B.Atajonova - ped.f.b. Ph.D, AndMI, Andijon O'zbekiston

Sh.A.Umarov - f.-m.f.b. Ph.D., TATU Farg'ona filiali, Farg'ona, O'zbekiston.

I.A.Rustamov - fal.f.b. Ph.D., TATU Farg'ona filiali, Farg'ona, O'zbekiston.

B.X.Tolipov - f.f.b. Ph.D., TATU Farg'ona filiali, Farg'ona, O'zbekiston.

O.X.Otaqulov – t.f.n., dotsent. TATU Farg'ona filiali, O'zbekiston

O.S.Raimjonova – t.f.b. Ph.D, dotsent, TATU Farg'ona filiali, O'zbekiston

R.A.Nurdinova – t.f.b. Ph.D, dotsent, TATU Farg'ona filiali, O'zbekiston

M.I.Ismoilov – t.f.b. Ph.D, dotsent, TATU Farg'ona filiali, O'zbekiston

I.T.Tojiboyev – t.f.n., dotsent, Farg'ona davlat universiteti, O'zbekiston

USE OF COMPUTER TOMOGRAPHY IN DENTISTRY. DENTO PROPRIETAS X-RAY

Abdurakhmonov S.A.
Tashkent Medical Academy
Anvarova D.G'
Tashkent Medical Academy

Annotation. Multispiral computed tomography, a modern medical technique, is highly effective in diagnosing diseases such as cancer, cardiovascular diseases, infectious diseases, injuries of the musculoskeletal system, and diseases of the musculoskeletal system. However, his diagnosis in the face-jaw area leads to the appearance of tumor diseases in patients. For this reason, we consider the Dento Proprietas X-ray setup based on the MSKT setup, the principle of operation of which is used to diagnose the maxillofacial area in dentistry. The lack of requirements for patients in the diagnostic process makes up for the shortcomings of previous diagnostic structures

Key words: Multispiral computed tomography, Dento Proprietas X-ray, stationary detectors, X-ray tube, diagnostics, scanning, hard and soft tissues

ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЕ КОМПЬЮТЕРНОЙ ТОМОГРАФИИ В СТОМАТОЛОГИИ. DENTO PROPRIETAS X-RAY

Абдурахмонов С.А.
Ташкентская медицинская академия
Анварова Д.Г.
Ташкентская медицинская академия

Аннотация. Мультиспиральная компьютерная томография — современный медицинский метод, высокоэффективный в диагностике таких заболеваний, как рак, сердечно-сосудистые заболевания, инфекционные заболевания, травмы опорно-двигательного аппарата, заболевания опорно-двигательного аппарата. Однако его диагностика в лице-челюстной области приводит к появлению у больных опухолевых заболеваний. По этой причине мы рассматриваем рентгеновскую установку Dento Proprietas на базе установки МСКТ, принцип действия которой используется для диагностики челюстно-лицевой области в стоматологии. Отсутствие требований к пациентам в диагностическом процессе компенсирует недостатки прежних диагностических структур.

Ключевые слова: мультиспиральная компьютерная томография, рентген Dento Proprietas, стационарные детекторы, рентгеновская трубка, диагностика, сканирование, твердые и мягкие ткани.

Introduction: Currently, it is impossible to imagine medicine without computer diagnostics. Technical progress and the advent of computers led to the development of tomographic methods, which today occupy a leading position in radiation diagnostics. The starting point for the development of radiation diagnostic methods was the advent of computed tomography (CT). In terms of its importance, the creation of CT is comparable to the discovery of X-rays. In 1998, another multispiral CT (MSKT) appeared in the development of CT. This is a type of computer tomography and is one of the most modern methods of viewing organs and tissues.

MSKT makes it possible to diagnose diseases such as cancer, cardiovascular diseases, infectious diseases, injuries of the musculoskeletal system, bleeding in organs and tissues, diseases of the musculoskeletal system. The main idea of MSKT is to use multiple array detectors in combination with x-ray broadening in the z-direction for more efficient use of X-rays. This shows that data can be collected from multiple images at the same time. Real-size images are captured in a short time. However, the radiation dose is high. Even dynamic processes can be evaluated. In MSKT, each detector element is divided into several small detector elements in z-direction. These detector elements form a 2D image. In MSKT, the thickness of the detector is not determined by X-rays. Instead, it is determined by the detector configuration. The length of each detector is often called detector collimation. The difference with an X-ray is that many pictures are taken and all of them are combined into a 3D model, which is much easier to view. MRI is used to scan bones and look for tumors. Bones are immediately visible on CT, and tumors are clearly visible when contrast is used. CT is especially important in severe conditions, such as a closed fracture with minor internal bleeding. We can quickly assess the severity of the situation. In case of extensive internal bleeding, emergency surgery is indicated immediately. Diagnosis of the condition of the heart and blood vessels. Damage to the skeletal structure, including the skull. Diagnosis of diseases of the excretory system - gastrointestinal tract, kidneys, bladder, liver, etc. (with or without contrast). It is used in the examination of tumors for relapses and in the diagnosis of diseases of the respiratory system.

Fig. 1 Multispiral computed tomography (MSKT)

The main advantage of MSKT is that it is a painless, non-invasive and informative research method. There is no residual radiation in the body after the examination and a short diagnostic time, retrospective creation of thinner or thicker sections from different data sets, and improved 3D rendering. In addition, MSCT is superior to MRI in terms of the quality of visualization of bone tissue. Unlike MRI, the presence of metal in the body is not a contraindication for the study. It is less sensitive to the patient's movements and allows for fast, real-time visualization of tissues. Current developments and trends point to more fractional systems driven by clinical applications possible through the use of such detectors.[1.2] We learned how important the role of MSCT in medical diagnostics is. But like all modern medical techniques, it has its own requirements and disadvantages:

- pregnancy is a clear contraindication for MSCT and is performed only for health reasons,
- nursing mothers should avoid feeding the baby for 24 hours after the injection of contrast material,
- risk of serious allergic reaction to iodine-containing contrast agents,
- MSKT in children should be done only when necessary and not repeated.

This structure, which has an important place in the field of medicine, affects patients differently during the diagnostic process due to the above-mentioned shortcomings, and these effects are harmfully hidden in their place. As medicine develops, different approaches to solving these problems are emerging. Diagnostic infusion of different parts of the head without affecting other organs of the body can provide a positive solution to the problems that arise. This method is mainly aimed at wide application in the field of stomatology. This is why, according to statistics, one out of every twenty patients with toothache is diagnosed with tumor diseases. Examples of these diseases are organospecific

malignant mesenchymal tumors, osteosarcoma, adenocarcinoma, squamous cell cancer, angiosarcoma, odontogenic tumors.

In this proposed method, maxillofacial diagnosis is performed using the Dento Proprietas x-ray device, which sees hard and soft tissues together. The DentoPR device is used in maxillofacial surgery. It is designed to see both soft and hard cells at the same time. Due to its low harm, it can be used for pregnant women, children under 14 years old and patients weighing more than 120 kg.

Figure 2. Dento Proprietas radiograph (DentoPR) setup

The structure of the device is based on the structure of MSKT. That is, the X-ray tube and the detector are rotated behind a circular curtain. A conical X-ray tube and array of stationary detectors are configured to achieve very high temporal resolution, high-speed tomography imaging from the electromagnetic deflection of the electron beam. In the device, the source and detector move along a spiral path relative to the object. A spiral can achieve improved image resolution compared to individual slice acquisition for a given radiation dose. The trajectory of spiral rays is characterized by its step[3.4]. This is divided by cross-sectional collimation equal to the transmission distance over the scan range per gantry rotation. In this case, the X-rays are cone-shaped, meaning that the X-rays trace a spiral trajectory relative to the object, and a set of two-dimensional detectors measure the object. The source and array of detectors are installed on the portal. The 220 V voltage is reduced through a transformer and fed to the receiving board. During the diagnostic process, the patient is lying down and the DentoPR device is installed in the jaw area of the head. Therefore, the diagnosis in the DentoPR setup led to the healing of other parts of the patient's body from radiation. In this

case, the X-ray tube and detectors are installed on the internal rotating part of the measuring (circular) section. Taking into account that the device is mainly used in diagnostics of the head part, the number of its detector lines and the energy of the emitted X-ray beam were taken into account[5.6]. This ensures that the negative impact of X-rays on patients is minimal. During the diagnostic process, the internal rotating part moves and the image becomes invisible on the screen through the interface. It can be seen that the DentoPR system is much more effective and less harmful than MSKT in the diagnosis of the head, especially the face and jaw.

Summary. Multi-spiral computed tomography is an important structure of modern tibiology in the diagnosis of diseases such as cancer, cardiovascular diseases, infectious diseases, injuries of the musculoskeletal system, bleeding in organs and tissues, diseases of the musculoskeletal system. But this structure, which has an important place in the field of medicine, affects patients differently due to the shortcomings it shows in the diagnostic process, and these effects are harmfully hidden in their place. Especially in the field of stomatology, most of the patients diagnosed with the facial part have tumors. As a modern solution to this, the Dento Proprietas x-ray system, which is based on the working principle of MSKT and which simultaneously sees hard and soft tissues in maxillofacial diagnostics, is shown. The simplicity of this method and the low requirements in the diagnostic process pave the way for a high level of service to patients and a great achievement in the field of medicine.

References

1. M. K. Bakhadirxhanov, N. F. Zikrillaev, K. S. Ayupov, D. T. Bobonov, F. A. Kadirova, and N. Il'khomzhonov Spectral Range of Current Self-Oscillation in Manganese-Doped Silicon Technical Physics, 2006, Vol. 51, No. 9, pp. 1235–1236
2. N.F. Zikrillaev, G.A. Kushiev, S.B. Isamov, B.A Abdurakhmanov, O.B. Tursunov. Photovoltaic Properties of Silicon Doped with Manganese and Germanium. J. Nano-electron. Phys. 15 №1, 01021 2023. N.F.Zikrillaev, G.A.Kushiev, Sh.I.Hamrokulov, Y.A.Abduganiev “Optical Properties of GexSi1-x binary compounds in silicon” Journal of nano- and electronic physics, Vol. 15, No. 3, pp. 03024-1 - 03024-4, 2023.
3. X.M. Iliyev, S.B. Isamov, B.O. Isakov, U.X. Qurbonova, and S.A. Abduraxmonov, “A surface study of Si doped simultaneously with Ga and Sb,” East Eur. J. Phys. 3, 303, 2023.
4. Iliyev, V.B. Odzhaev, S.B. Isamov, B.O. Isakov, B.K. Ismaylov, K.S. Ayupov, S.I. Hamrokulov, and S.O. Khasanbaeva, “X-ray diffraction and raman spectroscopy analyses of GaSb-enriched Si surface formed by applying diffusion doping technique,” East Eur. J. Phys. 3, 363 (2023).

5. Iliyev, X., Xudoynazarov, Z., Isakov, B., Uralbayev, X. and Kushiev, G., 2023. Impurity of atoms of manganese diffusion by outside electric field into silicon. Science and innovation, 2(A8), pp.107-111 B Isakov, Z Xudoynazarov, G Kushiev, A Sattorov, F Abduqahhorov, 2023. Thermodynamic conditions for the formation of gasb binary compound in Si sample. Science and innovation, 2(A10), pp.29-34.
6. N.F. Zikrillaev, G.A.Kushiev, S.V.Koveshnikov, B.A. Abdurakhmanov, U.Kh.Kurbanova, and A.A.Sattorov, "Current status of silicon studies with GexSi1-x binary compounds and possibilities of their applications in electronics" East European journal of physics, No. 3, pp. 334-339, 2023.
7. S Hamrokulov, G Kushiev, B Isakov, Z Umarkhodjaeva Digital microscope Analysis of chemically cleaned silicon surface Science and innovation, 2023. Т.2 №5 Pp.138-142 11. Абдурахманов Б.А., Исамов С.Б., Кушиев Г.А. Автоматизированная установка определения параметров полупроводников методом Ван Дер Пау. Приборы, 2022 №2. С.14-18.
8. N. F. Zikrillaev, O. B. Tursunov, G. A. Kushiev. "Development and Creation of a New Class of Graded-Gap Structures Based on Silicon with the Participation of Zn and Se Atoms". ISSN 1068-3755, Surface Engineering and Applied Electrochemistry, Vol. 59, No. 5, pp. 670–673. © Allerton Press, Inc., 2023

Tadqiq va tatbiq ilmiy-uslubiy jurnal	Research and implementation scientific-methodical journal	Исследования и внедрение научно-методический журнал
Tom 02. Son. 04. 2024	Vol. 02. Iss. 04. 2024	Том 02. Вып. 04. 2024

“Tadqiq va tatbiq” ilmiy-uslubiy jurnal

Tahririyat manzili:

150100, Farg‘ona vil., Farg‘ona sh., Solim ko‘chasi, 23/4-uy, 26-xonadon

E-mail:

chief_editor@fer-teach.uz

Bizning web-sahifa:

<https://fer-teach.uz/>

“Tadqiq va tatbiq” ilmiy-uslubiy jurnali "Fer-Teach" MChJ muassisligida tashkil etilgan bo‘lib, ilmiy va uslubiy jihatdan Muhammad al-Xorazmiy nomidagi Toshkent axborot texnologiyalari universiteti Farg'ona filiali tomonidan qo'llab-quvvatlanadi. Mazkur jurnal O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti Administratsiyasi huzuridagi Axborot va ommaviy kommunikatsiyalar agentligi tomonidan 2023-yil 3-mayda ommaviy axborot vositasi sifatida davlat ro'yxatidan (№ 078777) o'tkazilgan.

ISSN 3030-3362.

Jurnal aniq va tabiiy fanlar, ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy fanlar, texnika fanlari, tibbiyot fanlari, pedagogika fanlari sohalarini qamrab oladi. Tahrir hay'ati a'zolidan respublikaning turli OTMLarida faoliyat olib boruvchi fan nomzodlari va doktorlari o'rin olishgan..

Nashr tillari: O‘zbek, Rus, Ingliz va Qoraqalpoq tillari

Научно-методический журнал “ Исследования и внедрение ”

Адрес редакции:

150100, Ферганская область, г. Фергана, улица Солим, дом 23/4, кв. 26

E-mail:

chief_editor@fer-teach.uz

Наш сайт:

<https://fer-teach.uz/>

Учредителем научно-технического журнала

«Исследования и внедрение» является ООО “Fer-Teach”.

Журнал издается с 2023 года, зарегистрирован 3 мая 2023 года Агентством информации и массовых коммуникаций при Администрации Президента Республики Узбекистан (Сертификат № 078777).

ISSN 3030-3362.

«Исследования и внедрение» является специализированным журналом в области техники и охватывает все основные направления исследований и разработок в различных областях технических наук: физике, математике, информационных технологиях. В журнале также публикуются научные статьи по лингвистике, методике преподавания и истории развития технических наук.

Языки издания: Узбекский, русский, английский и каракалпакский

Tadqiq va tatbiq ilmiy-uslubiy jurnal	Research and implementation scientific-methodical journal	Исследования и внедрение научно-методический журнал
Tom 02. Son. 04. 2024	Vol. 02. Iss. 04. 2024	Том 02. Вып. 04. 2024

Scientific and methodological journal “Research and implementation”

Address:

150100, Fergana region, Fergana, Solim street, building 23/4, apt. 26

E-mail:

chief_editor@fer-teach.uz

Our website:

<https://fer-teach.uz/>

The scientific and methodological journal “Research and implementation” was founded by Fer-Teach LLC and supported by the Fergana branch of the Tashkent University of Information Technologies named after Muhammad al-Khorezmi. This journal was registered by the Agency of Information and Mass Communications under the Administration of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan on May 3, 2023 (No 078777).

ISSN 3030-3362.

"Research and implementation" is a specialized journal in the field of technology and covers all major areas of research and development in various fields of technical sciences: physics, mathematics, information technology. The journal also publishes scientific articles on linguistics, teaching methods and the history of the development of technical sciences.

Languages: Uzbek, Russian, English, Karakalpak

ВНИМАНИЕ!

При использовании материалов журнала необходимо указывать источник. Авторы статей несут ответственность за содержание статей и за сам факт их публикации.

Редакция не всегда разделяет мнения авторов и не несет ответственности за недостоверность публикуемых данных.

Редакция журнала не несет никакой ответственности перед авторами и/или третьими лицами и организациями за возможный ущерб, вызванный публикацией статьи.

ATTENTION!

When using journal materials, you must indicate the source.

The authors of the articles are responsible for the content of the articles and for the very fact of their publication.

The editors do not always share the opinions of the authors and are not responsible for the unreliability of the published data.

The editorial board of the journal does not bear any responsibility to the authors and / or third parties and organizations for possible damage caused by the publication of the article

DIQQAT!

Jurnal materiallaridan foydalanganda manbani ko'rsatish kerak.

Maqola mualliflari maqolalar mazmuni va ularning nashr etilishi fakti uchun javobgardirlar.

Har doim ham mualliflarning fikrlari tahririyat nuqtai nazarini ifodalamaydi va nashr etilgan ma'lumotlarning haqiqiyligi uchun javobgar emas.

Jurnal tahririyati mualliflar va/yoki uchinchi shaxslar va tashkilotlarga maqolaning e'lon qilinishi natijasida yetkazilishi mumkin bo'lgan zarar uchun javobgar emas.